

STUDYING THE PROCESS OF ABSORPTION AS A SIMULATION OBJECT

Fayzullaev B.A.¹, Toksanbaev K.M.², Tajibaev M.A.³

PhD.

¹⁻²⁻³Nukus Branch of Tashkent University of Information

Technologies named after Muhammad al Khwarizmi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7100642>

Abstract. The basic block diagram of the technological process of soda production is analyzed. The functional scheme of carbonation and absorption columns and the properties of the liquid and gas phases in the production of soda have been studied.

Functional relationships between the parameters of absorption and carbonation processes were considered as an object of mathematical modeling.

Keywords: absorption, carbonation column, pressure, mathematical model, concentration, flow rate, phase equilibrium

It is one of the most important products of the basic chemical industry. Soda ash is widely used in many industries, as well as for household needs.

The main raw materials for the production of soda ash are sodium chloride (salt) and calcium carbonate (limestone). On the territory of Uzbekistan, there are all the main types of raw materials for its production [1-6].

One of the typical modeling objects is the technological scheme of soda ash production (Fig. 1).

The main parameter of the absorption section is the flow of the filter liquid into the distillation column, which simultaneously determines the load of the absorption apparatus by the amount of absorbed ammonia. The main streams, including the purified brine for absorption and the water supplied to the cooling of the apparatus of the absorption station, are subordinate and are coordinated with the leading stream.

The main apparatuses of the carbonization department are the carbonization columns and the first column gas scrubber.

Fig. 1. Technological scheme of the production of soda ash. 1-brine cleaning, 2,4,12-pumps, 3-absorption department, 5-carbonization department, 6 filtration, 7-calcination department, 8 - roasting department, 9 quenching department, 10-compression department, 11-distillation, 13 - department of heavy soda

The carbonization (precipitation) column is a vertical cylindrical bubbling-type apparatus, consisting of separate cast-iron barrels and a drawer(similar to an absorption column) [2].

The first gas washer of the column (GWC-1) is a scrubber-type apparatus, which is a cylindrical hollow column with grates. In the upper part of the device there is a distribution irrigation plate. The dimensions of the washers are determined by the capacity of the carbonization section.

The control system of the carbonization department of the soda ash production solves the problem of optimal combination of high productivity of column equipment with high sodium and carbon dioxide utilization rates.

The functional relationship between the parameters of absorption and carbonization processes for the purpose of mathematical modeling can be represented in the following form:

$$Y = \phi\{X, Q, U, Z\} ;$$

Input parameters and state parameters at the moment of the process [3]:

$$X = (x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t)); \quad t_0 < t < t_1; \quad t \in T;$$

where $x_n(t)$ $n=1..N$ is the state vector of the system at the moment t (or the vector of phase coordinates);

$$Q = (q_i) \quad i = 1, \dots, I$$

where q_i are external parameters, which include the physicochemical properties of gas and liquids;

such as, q_1 - a - specific surface area (m^2 / m^3 or m^{-1});

which is determined using the formula:

$$a = \bar{c} \left(\frac{N_v \rho_{жс}}{\sigma^3} \right)^{0.2};$$

here $\bar{c} = \frac{\tau d_n}{\sigma}$; $d_n = \bar{c} \left(\frac{\sigma^3}{N_v \rho_{жс}} \right)^{0.2}$; $N_v = wg \rho_{жс}$; w - q_{14} , $\rho_{жс}$ - q_{16} , N_v - power per unit volume $\left(\frac{V_t}{m^3} \right)$, d_n - bubble diameter, σ - surface tension, N/m, τ - fictitious residence time, c;

q_2 - A - absorption factor,

$$A = \frac{l_0}{m}; \quad |A| = \frac{N_{ожс}}{N_{ог}}$$

l_0 - q_{10} , m - distribution coefficient and average value of the phase equilibrium constant; $N_{ог}$, $N_{ожс}$ are the total number of transfer units related to the gas or liquid phase.

q_3 - \bar{A} - is the concentration of the free (unbound) component A in the liquid, ($kmol/m^3$);

$$\bar{A} = \left[\frac{[M]^m [N]^n \dots}{K [B]^b [C]^c \dots} \right]^{1/a};$$

here K is the equilibrium constant, B, C, ... are molecules (or ions) in solution, M, N are reaction products; a, b, c, ..., m, n, ... are stoichiometric coefficients.

q_4 - a_e - effective contact surface (m^{-1});

$$a_e = \frac{\beta_{жсв}}{\beta_{жс}};$$

where $\beta_{жсв}$ - is the volumetric mass transfer coefficient in the liquid phase, $kmol/(m^3c)$ or (c^{-1}) ; $\beta_{жс}$ - is the mass transfer coefficient in the liquid phase;

q_5 - F - surface (m^2);

here a - q_1 ; V - volume, m^3 ;

q_6 - f - fugacity (volatility) of the component;

$$f'_0 = \gamma' P; \quad f_i = f_0 x_i \gamma_i;$$

here P is the hydraulic resistance, Pa; γ is the activity coefficient;

q_7 - h_r , h_l -- is the height of the transfer unit in the gaseous and liquid phases (m);

$q_8 - K_v$ - volumetric mass transfer coefficient;

$$K_g = Ka;$$

where $a - q_1$; K is the surface mass transfer coefficient;

$q_9 - t$ is time, c ;

$$t = \frac{l}{w_0} \bar{\varphi} = \frac{V_{an}}{V} \bar{\varphi};$$

where $u_5 - l_{an}$ is the apparatus length, m ; w_0 is the reduced flow rate, $\bar{\varphi}$ - is the fraction of the apparatus section occupied by the flow; V_{an} - is the working volume of the apparatus, V - is the volumetric flow rate;

Here $u_1 - L$ is the brine flow rate (m^3) (L is the liquid flow rate, ($kmol/s$ or kg/s), L_0 - is the carrier flow rate in the liquid phase, ($kmol/s$);

$u_2 - \theta$ is the temperature of the cooling agent, $^{\circ}C$.

$$dQ_0 = k' \bar{\psi} (v - \theta') dF ;$$

where Q - heat flux (kW), $v - q_{83}$, $\bar{\psi}$ - cooling surface, k - heat transfer coefficient between the medium in the absorber and the cooling agent;

$u_3 - P_g$ - gas pressure (Pa); P is the total pressure, Pa .

$$P = \frac{CRT}{y};$$

where $C - u_4$, $R = 8,31$ — gas constant, $kJ/(kmol \cdot K)$, T is the absolute temperature (K), y is the mole fraction in the gas;

ratio between partial and total pressures:

p is the partial pressure (Pa);

$$p = Py ;$$

where P - is the total pressure, y - is the mole fraction in the gas;

$u_4 - C_g$ - volume concentration of gas (n.d.).

C - concentration (mole volume), ($kmol/m^3$);

$$C = \frac{\bar{C}}{M_k}; \quad C = \frac{n_{\Gamma}}{An_{\text{жк}}};$$

where \bar{C} - the unit of volumetric concentration is kg/m^3 ; M_k is the molar mass (mass 1 $kmol$), $kg/kmol$; $n_g, n_1 - q_{10}$; $A - q_2$;

Y - is the relative molar concentration of the gas;

$$Y = \frac{C}{\frac{P}{RT} - \sum C}; \quad Y = \frac{y}{1 - \sum y};$$

where $C - C_g$ - volume concentration of gas (n.d.), $P - u_3$, $R = 8.31$ - gas constant, $kJ/(kmol \cdot K)$, T - absolute temperature (K), y - mole fraction in gas;

$$Z = (z_k); \quad k = 1, \dots, K;$$

where z_k – disturbing influence;

such as $z_1 - \nu$ — liquid temperature (low ammoniated brine and ammoniated brine) during absorption and carbonization ($^{\circ}\text{C}$);

$$G_0 c' dt_0 = \bar{\alpha} (\nu - t_0) dF ;$$

where G_0 – inert gas consumption, c' – heat capacity of the gas mixture, referred to 1 kmol of inert gas, $\bar{\alpha}$ – q_{15} , t_0 – gas temperature, $^{\circ}\text{C}$, F – q_5 ;

z_2 is the ambient temperature; z_3 is the CO_2 concentration of furnace gas; z_4 is the concentration of gas from the calcination section; z_5 – concentration ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{CO}_2$) of furnace gas; z_6 is the gas temperature from the calcination section; z_7 – temperature ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{CO}_2$) of furnace gas; z_8 - alkalis in the walls of cooling installations, formed in the process of absorption, etc.

Y - output data;

$$Y = (y_j); \quad j = 1 \dots J;$$

where y_j – ammoniated-carbonated brine output, sodium bicarbonate slurry and absorption off-gases ($\text{NaCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NH}_3$ and partly CO_2) carbonization off-gases ($\text{NaCl} + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NH}_3 + \text{CO}_2$).

Thus, here are presented some features of the technology for the production of soda ash as an object of mathematical modeling. The input, output, perturbing and control parameters of absorption and carbonization processes are given and analyzed for the purpose of mathematical modeling.

References:

1. Bepalov A.V., Kharitonov N.I. Control systems for chemical-technological processes. Yoshkar-Ola, Mari Printing and Publishing Plant, 2007
2. Krashennikov S.A. Technology of soda ash and purified sodium bicarbonate. Moscow, Higher School, 1985
3. Kaipbergenov, B.T., Fayzullaev, B.A., Elmuratov, M.K. Modeling of the Technological Process of Ammonization of Soda Production Under Conditions of Changing Initial Data, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, 2021, 1323 AISC, pp. 309–315
4. Mahmud S. M., Sadatdiyev K., Fayzullaev B.A. RENFIS-MA: A Recurrent Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System for Time Series Water Level Prediction. 2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT) DOI: 10.1109/ICISCT52966.2021.9670019
5. Kaipbergenov B.T., Fayzullaev B.A., Baynazarov A.Ya., Tajibaev M.A. To the Question of Studying liquid levels in the Columns of Carbonization of

soda Production. Science and Education in Karakalpakstan. No. 4/1 (19) 2021. Pp 128-134.

6. Bobozhonov, Y., Seytmuratov, B., Fayzullaev, B., & Sulstonov, A. (2020). Study of the influence of different designs of massive rotor of asynchronous generator on their maximum power. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 216, p. 01177). EDP Sciences. //E3S Web of Conferences. - EDP Sciences, 2020. - T. 216. - P. 01177.

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

